

http://plugin04.marketingdigitaltools.com/

NOVO TESTE

```

1 <!doctype html>
2 <html lang="pt-PT">
3
4 <head>
5     <meta charset="UTF-8">
6     <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, in
7     <link rel="profile" href="https://gmpg.org/xfn/11">
8
9     <title>Marketing Digital Tools | Agência de Marketing
10 <!-- The SEO Framework by Sybre Waaijer -->
11 <meta name="robots" content="max-snippet:-1,max-image-preview:
12 <meta name="description" content="Marketing Digital Tools | Ag
13 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin04.marketingdi
14 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin04.marketingdi
15 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin04.marketingdi
16 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin04.marketingdi
17 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin04.marketingdi
18 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin04.marketingdi
19 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin04.marketingdi
20 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin04.marketingdi
21 <meta property="og:locale" content="pt_PT" />
22 <meta property="og:type" content="website" />
23 <meta property="og:title" content="Marketing Digital Tools | A
24 <meta property="og:description" content="Marketing Digital To
25 <meta property="og:url" content="http://plugin04.marketingdigi
26 <meta property="og:site_name" content="Marketing Digital Tools
27 <meta name="twitter:card" content="summary_large_image" />
28 <meta name="twitter:site" content="@mktdigitaltools" />
29 <meta name="twitter:creator" content="@fogebandido" />
30 <meta name="twitter:title" content="Marketing Digital Tools |
31 <meta name="twitter:description" content="Marketing Digital To
32 <meta name="twitter:image" content="http://plugin04.marketingd
33 <link rel="canonical" href="http://plugin04.marketingdigitalto
34 <script type="application/ld+json">{"@context":"https://schema
35 <script type="application/ld+json">{"@context":"https://schema
36 <meta name="google-site-verification" content="sQBJ98u1EC3V5-8
37 <!-- / The SEO Framework by Sybre Waaijer | 3.46ms meta | 1.30
38 <link rel='dns-prefetch' href='//s.w.org' />
39 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
40 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
41     <script type="text/javascript">
42         window._wpemojiSettings = {"baseUrl":"https://s.
43         !function(e,a,t){var r,n,o,i,p=a.createElement("ca
44     </script>
45     <style type="text/css">
46 img.wp-smiley,
47 img.emoji {
48     display: inline !important;
49     border: none !important;
50     box-shadow: none !important;
51     height: 1em !important;
52     width: 1em !important;
53     margin: 0 .07em !important;
54     vertical-align: -0.1em !important;
55     background: none !important;

```

Detetada WebSite

0 ERROS 0 AVISOS 2 ITENS

WebSite	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
@type	WebSite				
WebSite url	http://plugin04.marketingdigitaltools.com/				
name	Marketing Digital Tools				
alternateName	Marketing Digital Tools				
potentialAction	SearchAction				
@type	SearchAction				
target	EntryPoint				
@type	EntryPoint				
urlTemplate	http://plugin04.marketingdigitaltools.com/search/{search_term_string}				
query-input	PropertyValueSpecification				
@type	PropertyValueSpecification				
valueRequired	http://schema.org/True				
valueName	search_term_string				